

VARIATIONS IN THE AIRBORNE POLLEN IN TWO ADJACENT URBAN LOCALITIES OF ALLAHABAD

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Using vertical cylinder spore traps two aeropalynological surveys were conducted for one year simultaneously in two adjacent urban localities of Allahabad to study the differences and similarities in the airborne pollen. Site I is located in the open area of Science Faculty of University of Allahabad while Site II is located in the adjacent crowded market of Katra. 3513.58 pollen grains/cm² belonging to 83 pollen types from Site I and 1330.86 pollen grains/cm² belonging to 64 pollen types from Site II were recorded during the one year survey. At both the sites highest pollen counts were registered in the month of March and lowest in July. Pollen grains of *Holoptelea integrifolia* were found highly dominant in both the localities (1776.23/825 pollen grains/cm²) followed by those of Poaceae (300/181 pollen grains/cm²). The similarity index between the two sites is 75%. Though both the sites are located in adjacent localities only about half a kilometer apart, their pollen calendars showed significant variations in the pollen counts which were correlated with the differences in the density and proximity of vegetation around the two sites.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of pollen grains as an aeroallergen and a cause of pollinosis is well established and documented¹⁻⁷. The diagnosis of pollinosis depends upon the knowledge of the time at which the patient is likely to be exposed to various allergenic pollen grains. Thus the information about pollen types and their pollination season is an essential pre-requisite for clinical application of allergy⁸⁻¹².

The composition and concentration of airborne pollen generally fluctuates from season to season and from place to place depending upon the diversity and density of the surrounding vegetation¹³⁻¹⁶. The pollen grains tend to be distributed in dense concentrations around their sources and therefore tend to be of local occurrence¹⁷. Hence, it is desirable to present airborne pollen spectra of far off localities, and such data made available for ready reference. Surveys of airborne pollen of far off localities are available for some cities of India¹⁸⁻²². In our knowledge no aeropalynological survey of adjacent urban localities has been conducted so far. However, one survey of summer airspora of two contrasting adjacent rural sites is available which is conducted by Lacey (1962) in Berkshire.

The paper presents first report on the incidence of airborne pollen grains in two adjacent urban localities. To study the variations in the airborne pollen spectra of two adjacent localities, day to day monitoring of airborne pollen was carried out for one year using vertical cylinder spore traps in the two localities of North Allahabad. Site I is located in the open area of Science Faculty of University of Allahabad while Site II is located in the adjacent crowded market area of Katra.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Using vertical cylinder spore traps day to day sampling of airborne pollen grains was carried out from October 2006 to September 2007 simultaneously at two sites. Vertical cylinder spore traps were installed at a height of 11 meters above the ground level at both the sites. Daily exposure of vertical glass rods (5mm) covered with glycerin jelly coated cellophane tapes (1.8 X 1.8 cm) was done.

The exposed tapes were mounted in safranin glycerin jelly on a slide under a cover slip of 20mm area.

Counting of pollen grains was done thoroughly in several vertical sweeps under a microscope. Pollen counts estimated in 3.24 cm² area were then converted to number per square cm.

The identification of pollen grains was done with the help of reference slides prepared from ground plants and published literature²³⁻²⁷. Site I (terrace of Morphology and Palaeobotany Laboratory) is located in the Roxburgh Botanical Garden of Science Faculty, University of Allahabad which is situated in an open area of North Allahabad. On its South lies Chandra Shekhar Azad Park with diverse vegetation while on the North is Site II (terrace of a building) at a crow flight distance of about 500 meters. Site II is located in a densely built up crowded market area of Katra having two-three storeyed buildings, with no significant vegetation around it. Ground floors are used for commercial purposes while higher floors are used mostly for residential purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composition and relative abundance

During one year survey altogether 82 pollen types from Site I and 64 pollen types from Site II were identified from the atmosphere of Allahabad (Table 1). At both the sites *Holoptelea integrifolia* ranked first in order of dominance contributing 50.55% (Site I) and 61.99% (Site II) to the pollen spectrum followed by Poaceae with 8.54% (Site I) and 13.61% (Site II) contribution.

At Site I other abundant types were *Ricinus communis* (3.14%), *Pinus roxburghii* (2.97%), *Azadirachta indica* (2.78%), *Ailanthus excelsa* (2.50%), *Madhuca longifolia* (2.22%), *Putranjiva roxburghii* (2.22%), *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae* (1.75%), *Roystonea regia* (1.28%), *Parthenium hysterophorus* (1.26%), *Anthocephalus cadamba* (1.17%), *Thuja occidentalis* (0.94%), *Caryota urens* (0.75%), Other Asteraceae (0.67%), *Brassica campestris* (0.68%) and *Typha angustata* (0.61%) while rest of the 67 types recorded less than 0.5% of the total catches (Fig.1).

At Site II *Azadirachta indica* (2.50%), *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae* (1.97%), *Ailanthus excelsa* (1.67%), *Ricinus communis* (1.60%), *Parthenium hysterophorus* (1.39%), *Brassica campestris* (0.97%), *Madhuca longifolia* (0.93 %),

Cannabis sativa (0.88%), *Putranjiva roxburghii* (0.81%), *Typha angustata* (0.77%), Other Asteraceae (0.63%) and *Anthocephalus cadamba* (0.60%) were the abundant types while rest of the 51 types were recorded in less than 0.5% of the total catches (Fig.1). Pollen grains of trees ranked first at both the localities quantitatively as well as qualitatively. Next in order of dominance are pollen grains of Poaceae followed by those of other herbs and shrubs. The data concerning the four groups of plants is presented in Table 2.

With respect to mode of pollination maximum pollen originated from anemophilous taxa represented by pollen grains of *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae*, *Artemisia* sp., *Cannabis sativa*, *Cyperaceae*, *Holoptelea integrifolia*, *Iberis amara*, *Pinus roxburghii*, *Poaceae*, *Ricinus communis*, *Thuja occidentalis*, *Typha angustata* etc.

Amphiphilous forms formed the second major part of spectrum represented by pollen grains of *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Caryota urens*, *Eucalyptus citridora*, *Prosopis juliflora*, *Putranjiva roxburghii*, *Roystonea regia*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Toona ciliata* etc.

Entomophilous pollen were least represented in the pollen spectrum with pollen grains of *Anthocephalus cadamba*, *Brassica* sp., *Cassia siamea*, *Euphorbia pulcherrima*, *Madhuca longifolia*, *Parthenium hysterophorus* etc.

It may be mentioned here that anemophilous taxa are represented by 15 & 12 types, amphiphilous by 17 & 16 types and entomophilous by 51 & 36 types at Site I & Site II respectively.

Pollen counts and seasonal distribution

Altogether 3513.58 pollen grains/cm² was recorded from Site I and 1330.86 pollen grains/cm² from Site II. Monthly and seasonal variations were observed in the pollen counts as well as in the pollen types (Figs. 2 & 3). Highest pollen counts were registered in the month of March (1939.20 pollen grains/cm² at Site I and 655.86 pollen grains/cm² at Site II). During March as high as 356.48 pollen grains/cm² at Site I and 336.73 pollen grains/cm² at Site II were recorded in a single day (Fig.4). Next highest monthly counts were observed in April (446.91 pollen grains/cm²) followed by February (406.48 pollen grains/cm²) at Site I and in February (258.64 pollen grains/cm²) followed by April (156.79 pollen grains/cm²) at Site II.

Table 1: Annual counts of airborne pollen grains at Site I and Site II during 2006-07.

S. No		SITES	TOTAL	Per cm ²
1.	<i>Acacia</i> sp.	I	11	3.40
		II	2	0.62
2.	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	1	0.31
3.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	3	0.93
4.	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	I	285	87.96
		II	72	22.22
5.	<i>Alnus</i> sp.	I	7	2.16
		II	2	0.62
6.	Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae	I	199	61.42
		II	85	26.23
7.	<i>Anthocephalus cadamba</i>	I	133	41.05
		II	26	8.02
8.	<i>Artemisia</i> sp.	I	43	13.27
		II	4	1.23
9.	Other Asteraceae	I	76	23.46
		II	27	8.33
10.	<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	1	0.31
11.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	I	317	97.84
		II	108	33.33
12.	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>	I	7	2.16
		II	2	0.62
13.	<i>Bauhinia</i> sp.	I	3	0.93
		II	0	0.00
14.	<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
15.	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	I	11	3.40
		II	0	0.00
16.	<i>Bougainvillea</i> sp.	I	0	0.00
		II	2	0.62
17.	<i>Brassica campestris</i>	I	77	23.77
		II	42	12.96
18.	<i>Cajanus cajan</i>	I	0	0.00
		II	1	0.31
19.	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i>	I	10	3.09
		II	5	1.54
20.	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	I	31	9.57
		II	38	11.73
21.	<i>Caryota urens</i>	I	85	26.23
		II	3	0.93
22.	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	1	0.31
23.	<i>Cassia nodosa</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	2	0.62
24.	<i>Cassia siamea</i>	I	35	10.80
		II	3	0.93
25.	<i>Celosia cristata</i>	I	14	4.32
		II	6	1.85
26.	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	I	6	1.85
		II	0	0.00
27.	<i>Chrysanthemum</i>	I	0	0.00

S. No		SITES	TOTAL	Per cm ²
	sp.	II	10	3.09
28.	<i>Convolvulus</i> sp.	I	19	5.86
		II	0	0.00
29.	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	I	0	0.00
		II	1	0.31
30.	<i>Coronopus didymus</i>	I	0	0.00
		II	3	0.93
31.	<i>Crateva nurvala</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
32.	<i>Croton bonplandianum</i>	I	11	3.40
		II	3	0.93
33.	<i>Cycas</i> sp.	I	3	0.93
		II	0	0.00
34.	Cyperaceae	I	35	10.80
		II	14	4.32
35.	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	0	0.00
36.	<i>Delonix regia</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
37.	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	7	2.16
38.	<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i>	I	50	15.43
		II	0	0.00
39.	<i>Euphorbia geniculata</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	1	0.31
40.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
41.	<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>	I	36	11.11
		II	0	0.00
42.	<i>Feronia limonia</i>	I	7	2.16
		II	3	0.93
43.	<i>Gelonium multiflorum</i>	I	5	1.54
		II	0	0.00
44.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i>	I	5755	1776.23
		II	2673	825
45.	<i>Iberis amara</i>	I	47	14.51
		II	0	0.00
46.	<i>Impatiens balsamina</i>	I	0	0.00
		II	1	0.31
47.	<i>Justicia simplex</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
48.	<i>Lagerstroemia indica</i>	I	7	2.16
		II	1	0.31
49.	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	I	253	78.90
		II	40	12.35
50.	Other Monocots	I	649	2.00
		II	28	8.64
51.	Malvaceae	I	1	0.31
		II	0	0.00
52.	<i>Monstera deliciosa</i>	I	4	1.23
		II	0	0.00

53.	<i>Morus alba</i>	I	8	2.47
		II	1	0.31
54.	<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	0	00
55.	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	0	00
56.	<i>Nigella sativa</i>	I	0	00
		II	1	0.31
57.	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	2	0.62
58.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	1	0.31
59.	<i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	0	00
60.	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	I	143	44.40
		II	60	18.52
61.	<i>Peltophorum roxburghii</i>	I	9	2.78
		II	0	00
62.	<i>Pithecolobium dulce</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	1	0.31
63.	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	I	338	104.32
		II	9	2.78
64.	Poaceae	I	972	300
		II	587	181.17
65.	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	I	15	4.62
		II	2	0.62
66.	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	I	11	3.40
		II	9	2.78
67.	<i>Portulaca sp.</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	2	00
68.	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	I	37	11.42
		II	12	3.17
69.	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	I	28	8.64
		II	5	1.54
70.	<i>Pterospermum acerifolium</i>	I	6	1.85
		II	1	0.31
71.	<i>Putranjiva roxburghii</i>	I	253	78.09
		II	35	10.80
72.	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	I	358	110.50
		II	69	21.13
73.	<i>Rorippa dubia</i>	I	4	1.23
		II	1	0.31
74.	<i>Roystonea regia</i>	I	146	45.06
		II	0	00
75.	<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	I	12	3.70
		II	2	0.62
76.	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	I	1	0.31
		II	1	0.31
77.	<i>Saraca asoca</i>	I	0	00
		II	1	0.31
78.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	I	3	0.93
		II	3	0.93
79.	<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	I	6	1.85
		II	2	0.62
80.	<i>Spergula fallax</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	0	00

81.	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i>	I	4	1.23
		II	0	00
82.	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	11	3.40
83.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	0	00
84.	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	I	0	00
		II	2	0.62
85.	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	I	107	33.02
		II	0	00
86.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	I	52	16.05
		II	12	3.70
87.	<i>Toona ciliata</i>	I	35	10.80
		II	18	5.56
88.	<i>Typha angustata</i>	I	69	21.30
		II	33	9.57
89.	Umbelliferae	I	2	0.62
		II	2	0.62
90.	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	I	15	4.63
		II	16	4.94
91.	<i>Zizyphus jujuba</i>	I	2	0.62
		II	0	00
	Unidentified	I	474	146.91
		II	190	59.26
	TOTAL (11cm ²)	I	11384	3513.58
		II	4312	1330.86

Table 2: Pollen counts in relation to habit of plants.

	SITE I			SITE II		
	No. of Taxa	Annual Total Catch		No. of Taxa	Annual Total Catch	
		Catch (/cm ²)	%		Catch (/cm ²)	%
Trees	44	2647.83	75.36	33	953.40	71.65
Grasses	1	300	8.54	1	181.17	13.61
Herbs	26	238.58	6.79	20	108.32	8.14
Shrubs	12	180.25	5.13	10	28.71	2.15

Fig 1: Pollen Spectra of Allahabad showing percentage contribution of important pollen types at Site I and Site II during 2006-07.

Lowest counts were registered in July at both the sites (15.74 pollen grains/cm² at Site I and 7.10 pollen grains/cm² at Site II). Qualitatively at Site I maximum number of pollen morphotypes (37 types) were registered in March and April and minimum in October and December (15 types) while at Site II April recorded

maximum number of pollen morphotypes (28 types) and October registered minimum number of pollen types (8 types). Pollen calendars show distribution of common pollen types recorded at Site I and Site II at Allahabad during 2006-07 (Figs.5 & 6).

With respect to pollen counts, qualitative as well as quantitative, the period of February to April (spring season) may be regarded as the principal pollen season. High pollen counts during this season were chiefly due to pollination season of arboreal taxa.

Major pollen contributors of this season were: arboreal taxa like *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Caryota urens*, *Holoptelea integrifolia*, *Madhuca longifolia*, *Pinus roxburghii* and *Putranjiva roxburghii*.

Among these *Ailanthus excelsa* showed peak occurrence in February, *Holoptelea integrifolia* in March while *Azadirachta indica*, *Madhuca longifolia* and *Putranjiva roxburghii* registered peak in April at both the sites. Dominance of pollen grains of *Caryota urens* and *Pinus roxburghii* was recorded at Site I only with the peak in April and March respectively.

Shrubs like *Ricinus communis* and *Thuja occidentalis* which recorded peak in March at Site I. At Site II *Ricinus communis* showed peak in February and *Thuja occidentalis* was altogether absent.

Grasses, pollen grains of which were found in varying concentrations throughout the year and showed one of the peaks in April at both the sites.

Weeds like *Parthenium hysterophorus* and those belonging to *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae*, their pollen were also recorded during most part of the year, registered peak occurrence in March at both sites. *Parthenium hysterophorus* registered peak in March at Site I (at Site II in October) and showed sporadic occurrence almost round the year at both the localities.

Herbs like *Brassica campestris* and *Iberis amara* recording peak occurrence in February - March respectively at Site I while at Site II *Brassica campestris* recorded the peak a little earlier in January and *Iberis amara* was found altogether absent from Site II. *Typha angustata* registered peak in April at both the sites.

Among the other types of both the localities *Convolvulus* sp., *Prosopis juliflora* *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Toona ciliata* were found in good numbers during this period at Site I. August to October (Post-monsoon) was another high pollen concentration period. About 11.23% (Site I) and 11.15% (Site II) of the total annual pollen catches were recorded during August to October. *Poaceae* was the major pollen contributor during this season showing highest pollen counts in October.

Pollen grains of weeds belonging to *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae* and *Parthenium hysterophorus* were also found present in the atmosphere in good numbers. At Site II, *Parthenium hysterophorus* recorded peak occurrence in October.

During this period pollen grains of trees like *Anthocephalus cadamba* recorded their occurrence in August at both the sites and those of *Roystonea regia*, which were recorded from Site I only, registered peak in September.

Among other types pollen grains of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Cyperaceae* were also found well represented in the atmosphere during this period at Site I.

The two high pollen frequency period alternate with two low pollen periods of May to July (July to June at Site II) and November to January recording 5.19% and 4.10% annual pollen catch at Site I and 1.51% and 4.45% annual pollen catch at Site II respectively.

Comparative analysis of two aeropalynological surveys of adjacent sites

Out of 83 pollen types recorded from Site I, 55 pollen types were found common at both the sites. Pollen grains of *Holoptelea integrifolia* were highly dominant in both the localities (1776.23/825 pollen grains/cm²) followed by those of *Poaceae* (300/181 pollen grains/cm²). Other dominant types (total annual catch more than 10grains/cm²) of both the localities were *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Amaranthaceae/Chenopodiaceae*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Brassica* sp., *Cannabis sativa*, *Madhuca longifolia*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Putranjiva roxburghii*, *Ricinus communis* and *Typha angustata*. Among the remaining pollen types common at both the localities, *Anthocephalus cadamba*, *Artemisia* sp., other *Asteraceae*, *Caryota urens*, *Cassia siamea*, *Cyperaceae*, *Pinus roxburghii*, *Prosopis juliflora*, *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Toona ciliata* were found in dominant numbers at Site I while at Site II they were present in lesser numbers (<10 pollen grains/cm²). Table 1 presents the pollen types and their monthly pollen counts at Site I & Site II during 2006-07. Some pollen types were of local occurrence, found present at one site only.

Fig 2: Monthly quantitative variation in the pollen counts at the two sites during 2006-07.

Fig 3: Monthly qualitative variation in pollen types at the two sites during 2006-07

Fig 4: Daily variations in total airborne pollen grains at Allahabad during 2006-07.

Fig. 5: Pollen Calendar of Allahabad at Site I during 2006-07.

Fig. 6: Pollen Calendar of Allahabad at Site II during 2006-07.

Table 3: Index of similarity and dissimilarity in the composition of pollen flora of two sites.

Pollen Types			Similarity Index $S=2C/A=B$	Dissimilarity Index (1-S)	% of Similarity Index	% of Dissimilarity Index
Site I (A)	Site II (B)	Common (C)				
83	64	55	0.75	0.25	75	25

Pollen types recorded from Site I only includes pollen grains of *Eucalyptus citridora*, *Euphorbia pulcherrima*, *Iberis amara*, *Roystonea regia* and *Thuja occidentalis* which were recorded in dominant numbers and *Bauhinia variegata*, *Boerhaavia diffusa*, *Bombax ceiba*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Convolvulus* sp., *Crateva religiosa*, *Cycas* sp., *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Delonix regia*, *Euphorbia heterophylla*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Gelonium multiflorum*, *Justicia simplex*, *Monstera deliciosa*, *Mirabilis jalapa*, *Murraya koenigii*, *Parkinsonia aculeata*, *Peltophorum roxburghii*, *Spergula fallax*, *Strychnos nux-vomica*, *Tamarindus indica*, and *Ziziphus jujuba* which were in stray numbers.

Pollen types present at Site II only includes stray pollen grains of *Bougainvillea* sp., *Cajanus cajan*, *Chrysanthemum* sp., *Citrus* sp., *Coronopus didymus*, *Impatiens balsamina*, *Nigella sativa*, *Saraca asoka* and *Terminalia arjuna*.

Index of similarity and dissimilarity is calculated to assess the diversity in the composition of two sites. The similarity index between the two sites is 75% (Table 3). Comparative analysis of the pollen data of the two sites revealed significant quantitative variations in the pollen counts. Though both sites are located in adjacent localities only about half a kilometer apart, pollen flora of Site I was found richer than Site II and recorded three fold pollen catch as compared to that of Site II. This may be correlated with the differences in the density and proximity of vegetation around the two sites. Site I, located in the Botanical Garden is surrounded by rich vegetation comprising of various garden ornamentals, trees, grasses and weeds while the Site II is located in densely built up market area having two-three storied buildings situated on either side of the road. There is no significant vegetation in the immediate vicinity of the Site II except for a few ornamentals like *Bougainvillea* sp., *Chrysanthemum* sp., *Impatiens balsamina*, *Ocimum sanctum* etc which are found growing on the terrace of adjacent buildings. Nearest trees around Site II are *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Delonix regia*, *Ficus religiosa* and *Holoptelea integrifolia* which are at a distance of about 100 meters from the sampling site. Densely built area of Site II having two-three storied buildings might have acted as physical barriers for the transport of pollen grains.

CONCLUSION

The present comparative aeropalynological study of the two adjacent urban sites revealed significant variations in their pollen counts. Diversity as well as proximity of source plants to Site I may be accounted for the higher incidence of pollen grains both quantitatively and qualitatively at Site I. Thus it may be concluded that the airborne pollen flora of adjacent localities may show variations depending upon the density, diversity and distribution of source plants around the sampling sites. Airborne pollen grains tend to be distributed around sources as suggested by Gregory (1983).

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